

Table Mechanisms of energetic compound (EC) immobilization by biochar

Method / Mechanism	Essence of the Mechanism	Examples (ECs / Conditions)	References
Electrostatic interaction	Attraction/repulsion between charged biochar surface and ionizable ECs; controlled by pH and ionic strength; generally minor for nitro-explosives	Limited pH effect (4–10) for TNT, DNT, RDX; Cu ²⁺ /Zn ²⁺ reduce TNT adsorption; competitive adsorption among TNT/DNT/RDX	(Lingamdinne et al., 2015; S.-Y. Oh & Seo, 2016);
Hydrophobic interaction	Partitioning of neutral/hydrophobic ECs onto hydrophobic carbon surface; enhanced in high-temperature and alkali-activated biochars; dominant mechanism	Increased adsorption of TNT, DNT, RDX after hydrophobic modification	(Gong et al., 2026; S.-Y. Oh & Seo, 2019, 2016)
Hydrogen bonding	H-bond formation between –OH/–COOH groups and electronegative atoms (O, S, F) in ECs; secondary role in nitro-explosive adsorption	Negative or weak correlation with TNT/DNT adsorption	(Dai et al., 2020; Regkouzas & Diamadopoulos, 2019)
π-π electron donor–acceptor (EDA) interaction	Interaction between π -electron-rich biochar graphitic domains and π -electron-deficient nitroaromatics; key adsorption mechanism	Stronger adsorption of DNT > TNT; adsorption of nitroaromatics (TNT, DNT); metal (Cu ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺) competition via M ²⁺ - π interaction	(Ji et al., 2022; S.-Y. Oh & Seo, 2019, 2014, 2016)
Redox-mediated reduction (electron shuttling)	Graphitic conductivity and redox-active groups (quinones, carbonyls, Fe/Mn) facilitate electron transfer and reduction of nitro-ECs	Biochar-enhanced DTT reduction of 2,4-DNT and RDX (>90% removal); AQDS-enhanced TNT/RDX degradation; biochar–Fe(0) composites	(S.-Y. Oh et al., 2017); (Xing et al., 2022)
Oxidant activation (AOP-like processes)	Surface functional groups activate persulfate/peroxide to generate •OH and SO ₄ • radicals; enhanced by metal or heteroatom modification	Persulfate-driven degradation of persistent organics; improved after acid/base or metal modification	(Yan et al., 2015)